

Skills list for the Open Science workshop

Skill name	Explanation
Adherence to the FAIR data principles during and after research	It is important that research data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR). During the active phase of research think about making data FAIR to colleagues from within the research team, to the supervisor, to external collaborators, to whoever might continue working on that research in the future. When making data FAIR after the end of the project, think about making data as open as possible, as closed as necessary; think about the use of data repositories, metadata standards, licensing, persistent identifiers etc.
Making use of open data from other researchers	Think about searching, re-using and encouraging re-use of already existing datasets: from the same team, external collaborators or publicly available repositories.
Adherence to good code management practices	Code needs to be properly managed and documented, ideally using environments that allow for version control, effective collaboration and provenance tracking.
Using or developing research tools open for reuse by others	Code / software supporting analyses or underlying research results should be made as open as possible, as closed as necessary. Think about using or developing open source code where possible, think about sharing any code developed openly, think about appropriate re-use licences, think about citation practices and the use of persistent identifiers.
Securing funding for open science / support	To ensure sustainability of open science activities, funding is necessary. Think about budgeting for the costs of open science activities (e.g. data and code archiving in open repositories, open source software development) in grant applications or about hiring dedicated support staff (e.g. data managers, research software engineers). You can also think about applying for dedicated funding to promote open science activities, events, training etc.
Recognizing and acknowledging the contribution of others	Think about recognising and acknowledging other people who contributed to greater openness of research projects: people whose data or code were re-used, people who helped with collection, management, documentation, publication and archiving of data, code and methods etc. Think about acknowledgement by citations, authorship, new collaborations.
Awareness and adherence to relevant ethical and legal policies	Think about the ethical and legal implications of open science: adherence to contractual obligations when working with public funders, private funders, commercial companies and when managing public/private partnerships. Think about implications of working with personal data.
Developing a vision and strategy on how to integrate OS practices in the normal practice of doing research	Think about ways of encouraging and ensuring adoption of open science practices within the immediate research team, by research collaborators, or by entire research communities. Think about good practice case studies, policies, workflows, practice exchange and also training and advocacy.
Being a role model in practising open science	Actively practising open science in a manner appropriate to one's career stage and serving as an example for others to follow. Think also about participating in working groups on open science, dedicated programmes (such as data champions, open science champions), giving talks on open science etc.